

DIDACTIC FOUNDATIONS FOR FORMING THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF THE FUTURE TEACHER

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ABSTRACT

The article considers the didactic competence of an educator as one of the key components in the structure of professional educational competence. A theoretical analysis of the concepts of "pedagogical" and "didactic" competence is given. It also reveals the content, levels and areas of competence that are part of didactic competence.

At present, in connection with the transition to new standards of education at school, one of the acute problems is the issue of training highly qualified personnel. A number of requirements are imposed on the personality of the educator in a modern school, but we are more interested in the content of the professional competence of the future educator.

One of the important aspects of the learning process is the question of the teacher's readiness to effectively organize the learning process (didactic process). Therefore, the main goal of this article is an attempt to determine the place of didactic competence in the structure of professional educational competence of an educator, to define the concept of "didactic competence" and to conduct a theoretical analysis of the study of this issue at the present time.

It should be noted that the issue of the formation of professional competence of a specialist is studied by many educators and psychologists from the standpoint of an activity approach - the unity of personality, consciousness and activity, the relationship between the processes of activity and communication (K.A. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, B.G. Ananiev, A.A. Bodalev, V. V. Davydov, L. S. Vygotsky, P. Ya. Galperin, I. A. Zimnyaya, A. A. Leontiev, A. N. Leontiev, S. L. Rubinstein and others).

The study of professional and educational competence is an actual area of activity for a number of scientists (N.V. Kuzmina, I.A. Zimnyaya, A.K. Markova, V.N. Vvedensky, M.I. Lukyanova, A.V. Khutorskoy, G. S. Sukhobskaya, O. N. Shakhmatova, V. A. Slastenin).

Kuzmina N.V. in professional and educational competence, includes five elements or types of competence: special-pedagogical, methodological, socio-psychological, differential-psychological, autopsychological. Methodological competence covers the area of ways of forming knowledge, skills in students [4].

Angelovski K. in his works highlights the structure of the teacher's professional competence through educational skills. These educational skills can be combined into four groups: [1, p.63].

1. The ability to "translate" the content of the objective process of education into specific educational tasks: the study of the individual and the team to determine their preparedness for the active mastery of new knowledge and design on this basis the development of the team and individual students; allocation of a complex of educational, upbringing and developing tasks, their concretization and determination of the dominant task;
2. Ability to build and set in motion a logically completed educational system: integrated planning of educational tasks; reasonable choice of forms, methods and means of its organization;
3. The ability to identify and establish relationships between the components and factors of education, to put them into action: the creation of the necessary conditions (material, moral, mental, organizational, etc.); activation of the student's personality, development of his activities; and etc;
4. Skills for accounting and evaluating the results of educational activities: introspection and analysis of the educational process and the results of the teacher's activities; definition of a new set of dominant and subordinate tasks.

Analyzing the scientific literature, we came to the conclusion that many scientists studying the problem of educator's competence use the term "professional competence" in their research [7, p. 9], then the term "pedagogical competence", sometimes both terms, and sometimes combine these terms.

At present, there is no single approach to the definition of this concept in science. So, according to V.A. Slastenina, I.F. Isaeva, A.I. Mishchenko and E.N. Shiyanov, the professional competence of the educator expresses readiness to carry out educational activities, while the basis of the structure of the educator's competence is formed by numerous educational skills that characterize this readiness [3, p.9].

We settled on the following definition of educational competence.

So, pedagogical competence is a systemic phenomenon, the essence of which lies in the systemic unity of educational knowledge, experience, properties and qualities of the educator, allowing to effectively carry out educational activities, purposefully organize the process of educational communication and also imply personal development and improvement of the educator [3, p.10].

Our scientific interest is directed to didactic competence, which is an integral part of the professional competence of an educator. The main component of the content content of the concept of "professional competence" of the future educator is didactic competence.

General didactic competencies can be noted in different classifications, for example, in Khutorsky they are part of educational and cognitive competencies (goal setting, planning, analysis, reflection, self-assessment of educational and cognitive activity.). Zimnyaya I.A. they will single out such a type of competencies as activity competencies: play, study, work; means and methods of activity: planning, design, modeling, forecasting, research activities, orientation in various activities.

Also, such a type of competence as didactic competence, in our opinion, is included in the composition of methodological competence in the field of methods of forming knowledge, the ability of students, which at one time is an element of professional and educational competence according to N.V. Kuzmina.

Investigating the scientific works devoted to the issue of the formation of the didactic competence of a practicing educator, we found that this problem has not yet been sufficiently studied. The works of S.N. Gorycheva, M.P. Endzin [2], Yu.V. Makhova [5], V.V. Serikov [8], as well as the development of the didactic competence of a university teacher, the study of E.V. Temple [9].

The relevance of studying the didactic competence of a teacher is justified by the fact that the number of scientific sources found indicates the insufficient development of this problem in educators.

The didactic competence of a teacher is an integral, key part of professional educational competence as a generalized complex characteristic of the level of professionalism, which reveals itself in the nature of the educator's subjectivity in the organization of the didactic process [6].

So Yu.V. Makhova highlights that the didactic competence of the educator is an integral part of professional competence as a generalized complex characteristic of the level of professionalism, which reveals itself in the organization of the didactic process. In other words, didactic competence can be characterized as the ability of an educator to solve complex professional problems that arise in the organization of the learning process, in accordance with the available knowledge, skills, and experience. [5, p.47].

M.N. Pevzner, O.M. Zaichenko, S.N. Gorycheva in her monograph "Scientific and methodological support of school personnel: educational consulting and supervision" (2002) distinguishes three levels of didactic competence: reproductive, heuristic, creative.

The reproductive level of didactic competence of a university teacher is determined by such characteristics of the organization of the learning process as stereotyping of activities (clear adherence to patterns, a limited set of methods and forms), the use of ready-made teaching technologies, positioning oneself only in the context of the subject being taught, and low motivation. Here, a normative-adaptive, invariant, clearly structured non-personal component is clearly manifested.

The heuristic level of didactic competence is characterized by the variability and effectiveness of the technologies used, teaching methods and techniques, the rejection of stereotypes in activities, the critical rethinking of one's experience in order to improve it, and the use of creative thinking techniques.

The creative level of the teacher's didactic competence is manifested in the subjectivity of the teacher in organizing the didactic process. The teacher uses an individual style of activity, solves educational problems at the level of modern effective theories and technologies for designing and modeling the learning process (system modeling), is able to design and improve his own technologies, is actively involved in innovative activities, adapts flexibly to changes.

Based on the analysis of the presented interpretations, we can single out that the didactic competence of a teacher is, first of all, an integral part of professional educational

competence, which characterizes the area of teacher competence related to the readiness to effectively organize the didactic process (learning process).

In our opinion, the area of competence included in didactic competence includes: special knowledge (subject), subject-didactic, psychological-educational, organizational, consulting.

These competence facets can be further differentiated into separate areas of competence:

- subject knowledge in an in-depth understanding of the subject;
- subject-didactic knowledge in students' ideas about the subject, knowledge of tasks, knowledge of how to explain;
- psychological and educational knowledge of methods, knowledge of the educational process;
- organizational knowledge about how to lead a class.

It should be noted that this assumption needs further research.

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